

A BRIEF REVIEW OF EDUCATIONAL THERAPY & ITS CURRENT ROLE

Part II

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The Professional Role of an Educational Therapist

What then is the professional role of an ET? What are the do's and don'ts for ETs in their professional practice?

An ET has multiple roles of responsibility. According to the Association of Educational Therapists (AET), to teach particular strategies to address the specific deficit(s) of individuals with learning challenges, it is a must for ETs to possess a good foundation in an academic subject, especially in language and literacy skills, mathematics and numeracy skills, and specialized knowledge and understanding of diverse learning disabilities (e.g., autism spectrum disorder, literacy disabilities or disorders).

Here are several key occupational roles that require ETs to perform professionally:

- Addressing all aspects of the learning experience, which includes academic, social, and emotional aspects;
- Communicating with people (e.g., family members and friends of the client) and other professionals, as well as employers (if the client is already working) who play significant roles in a client's life;
- Finding out how the underlying learning issues impact other areas of academic, social, or family dynamics in the client's daily routine;
- Fostering independence and self-advocacy in the client, helping him/her to take control of his/her learning process;
- Administering appropriate assessments and integrating the results to develop a wide range of applicable strategies for remedial teaching or intervention;
- Performing an academic screening or progressive evaluation when it is necessary;
- Providing support for the client's emotional and social development;
- Referring a client to other specialists if it deems necessary that the client is best served by a different allied professional or specialist; and/or
- Empowering the client's parents or guardians through collaborative consultation and/or coaching which, in turn, can support EdTx treatments.

Because EdTx can be very broad in its treatment approach, it becomes important to look at an ET's qualifications when seeking or hiring one. The ET should meet the client's learning needs and should, of course, possess adequate professional training and relevant working experience to cover a diversified range of individuals with different learning challenges. Thus, a qualified ET is expected to:

- Be acquainted with a diverse range of learning as well as

behavioral challenges;

- Know how to engage with clients with learning and behavioral differences;
- Possess expertise in an academic subject area or skill (e.g., reading, mathematics, and/or organizational skills); and/or
- Understand how socio-emotional-behavioral issues can impact a client, especially if he/she is still schooling.

In addition to having relevant extensive training and related working experience, ETs also administer formal and informal assessments, develop individualized education plans (IEPs), set short-term and long-term goals and objectives, and teach the clients using varied strategies to address challenges in the areas of reading, writing, spelling, mathematics, organization, and study skills. As such, ETs can offer services to meet the diversified needs of their clients with various learning and/or behavioral challenges, which include the following, but not limited to poor executive functioning skills (e.g., poor or short attention-concentration span, poor memory retention, slow information processing, poor organizational skills, poor ideation and planning), weak gross and/or fine psychomotor skills, negative learning inertia (e.g., laziness, procrastination, lacking in motivation or interest), and low self-esteem.

In this way, ETs can address the underlying deficit skills that affect academics (e.g., visual & auditory processing, attention, memory, and focusing), perform careful observations on their clients' behavior, assessment, and evaluation, and also develop IEP.

One of the most important roles that ETs do is to promote self-regulated learning of individuals with learning disabilities. They provide strategies on how to deal with academic challenges with motivation to utilize the right strategies at the right time (Newman, 2008). According to Connell and Wellborn (1991), ETs can help self-regulated learners to develop motivation in their learning around three personal needs. They are (1) involvement, (2) autonomy, and (3) competence. Interestingly, the authors of this article have proposed their framework of these three needs that are, in turn, based on three different theories: (1) Margaret Schönberger Mahler's (b.1897-d.1985) theory of separation-individuation in child development; (2) Jean William Fritz Piaget's (b.1896-d.1980) theory of cognitive development; and (3) Erik Homburger Erikson's (b.1902-d.1994) theory of psychosocial development (as shown in Figure 3 below). Together, the three theories can be triangulated to constitute self-regulated learning.

Figure 3. A Proposed Framework on Self-Regulated Learning with 3 Personal Needs

Some Misconceptions about ETs

As the professional roles of ETs are still cloudy, there are many misconceptions about them. Are they just like tuition teachers (or tutors)? Are they special education teachers? Or are they somewhat parapsychologists? These are some of the common questions that parents and the general public have always asked or have been wondering about. Table 1 below briefly shows the do's and don'ts of ETs' roles.

Table 1. The Do's and Don'ts of ETs' Roles

Do's of ETs	Don'ts of ETs
Refer clients to other allied professionals (SLTs, OTs, PTs, etc.) for further assessments.	Diagnose, assess, or prescribe medication for any medical conditions.
Describe behaviors to parents and allied professionals regarding clients' conditions (e.g., ASD, ADHD, Tourette syndrome, etc.).	Administer intelligence or other psychological tests.
Interpret and analyze tests and assessment reports from allied professionals and share results with parents/caregivers.	Practice psychotherapy and/or hypnosis.

Some parents may equate ETs with tutors and they have mistakenly thought that both are pedagogists or teaching academics. Although both may seem to be working on the same educational domain, i.e., academics, there are distinct differences between the two groups of professionals. Table 2 below further explains the main differences between traditional tutoring and EdTx.

Table 2. Differences between Traditional Tutoring and EdTx

Traditional Tutoring	Educational Therapy
Deals specifically with homework/academics (subject matter) with the aim of gaining a higher score on a test/examination.	Deals with the processing of information that enhance academic learning.
Uses restricted methodologies and employs structured teaching materials.	Uses a variety of methodologies and employs several teaching materials.
May or may not have experience working with people with learning disabilities (e.g., autism, dyslexia, ADHD, etc.).	Experience working with people with learning disabilities (special education teachers, reading/math specialists, counselors, etc.).
Does not possess knowledge and teaching experience in different learning disabilities and lacks the experience to identify red flags in areas of learning.	Possess knowledge and teaching experience in different learning disabilities with the ability to identify red flags and assess needs in areas of learning.
Does not possess knowledge & experience to conduct screening, assessment, evaluation, and remediation.	Possess knowledge & experience to conduct screening, assessment, evaluation, and remediation.

Conclusion

This article took a threefold standpoint: Firstly, the authors traced the German origin of EdTx, which was later transferred to the USA and the UK, which used different terms to describe

this form of treatment. The development of EdTx involving three domains – education, psychology, and therapy – came into play with the proposed model of "Tripartition of Education-Psychology-Therapy" (see Figure 1). Secondly, the roles of an ET are also explored and briefly described in terms of how ETs work with individuals with disabilities. The authors also put forth their framework on how ETs can help self-regulated learners to develop motivation in their learning around three personal needs: involvement, autonomy, and competence. Their framework relates three personal needs to three different theories (Mahler's theory of separation-individuation, Piaget's theory of cognitive development, and Erikson's theory of psychosocial development). Finally, the professional boundaries of ETs (i.e., do's and don'ts) are tabulated in Table 1 as well as some common misconceptions between traditional tutoring and EdTx are also differentiated in Table 2.

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